

The Praise of the Bees, Exultet Hymn

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Entry tags: Catholic text, Ritual text, Medieval Christianity, Religious Practice, Religious History, Christian Traditions, Hagiography, Monasticism, Text, Religious Group, Catholic, Early Christianity, Roman Catholic

The medieval hymn Exultet was probably compiled around the 5th - 6th century by an unknown author (probably Saint Augustine, Ambrose, or Jerome). It was chanted before the paschal candle during the Easter Vigil in the Roman Rite of Mass (Easter Proclamation). It was named after the first word of the hymn Exultet iam angelica turba coelorum...and contains references to resurrection and eschatology. of special and particular interest is the part of the hymn known as the Praise of the Bees, which forms an exclamation of the insect as creator of the holy wax, the honey, and as a symbol of Virgin Mary due to its reputed -then- physical chastity. There were two textual versions of the hymn, the earliest Beneventan and the later Franco-roman version. Illustrated scrolls of the hymn were created in monasteries in southern Italy from the early 10th to 15th century.

Date Range: 500 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Southern Italy

Region tags: Europe, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Italy, Byzantium

medieval monasteries of southern Italy

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: see bibliography

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.facsimilefinder.com/facsimiles/exultet-roll-facsimile>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WyEAsiDjFP4>

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/ExultetrevisedTranslation>

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.associationofcatholicpriests.ie/2011/03/the-exultet-old-new-and-latin/>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: parchment, folded as a scroll

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: probably not

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: the medieval Exultet rolls are considered high-valued artistic manuscripts

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– No

Shrine

– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– Yes

Notes: some of them are stored at their initial place of creation, that is medieval monasteries in south Italy

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops
– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: some are stored at Libraries in Europe (Paris, Manchester and in Italy)

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: there are medieval mosaics in some of the monasteries that they were created and up today stored.

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: usually they are designed schematically large, bereft of emotions with dilated pupils

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: a large number of saints and holy figures, both males and females

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)
– I don't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes
Notes: there are scenes of Christ's Life

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes
Notes: crosses

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)
– I don't know

↳ Humans
– Yes
Notes: there are saints and holy figures

↳ Supernatural narratives
– Yes
Notes: there are scenes of Christ's Life

↳ Human narratives
– Yes

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?
– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?
– Yes

Notes: most probably there was a collaboration of church and political authorities for their creation

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– I don't know

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: most probably

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: most probably the local governors of south-italian regions

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: most probably

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– I don't know

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: They were at the time of each manuscript's creation

↳ Present full-time?

– I don't know

↳ Present part-time?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: males

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– I don't know

Notes: probably Greek or Italian

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– I don't know

Notes: probably very well educated

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

Notes: probably of high rank

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– I don't know

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– I don't know

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– I don't know

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious

specialists?
– I don't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: it is accompanied with religious music

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: parts of the hymn were altered and specifically, the Praise of the Bees, was abolished.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: mainly deacons and priests in general; certainly (male) people of church education

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: males

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

Notes: probably italian; the initial language of the hymn was latin

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– I don't know

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: latin, however there were two main script versions: the earliest was the Beneventan one and the later, the Franco-roman one.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

- ↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?
– I don't know
- ↳ Possess its own distinct written language?
– No
- ↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?
[Select all that apply]
– Other [specify]: probably, high ranking priests
- ↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?
– I don't know
Notes: probably political authorities of that (medieval) time
- ↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?
– Yes
Notes: the hymn text was translated and studied in many european languages
- ↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?
– I don't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– I don't know

Notes: attendees of a liturgy held within a church.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– I don't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: it was chanted from the ambo of the church held by a deacon and unfolded so as the people could see the illustrations of the manuscript

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: it should; illustrations must have had at least a visual effect

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– I don't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: the hymn was chanted before the paschal candle during the Easter Vigil in the Roman Rite of Mass

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– I don't know

Notes: the attendees of a liturgy within a church

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: once a year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: it is considered a holy text however

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: 33 manuscripts of medieval era (10th-15 centuries) are richly illustrated

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: in latin

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: see below Illuminations

↳ Illuminations?

– Yes

↳ Is there spiritual value associated with the coloration?

– Yes

↳ Is there gold?

– Yes

↳ Other forms of illumination?

– Specify: scenes, holy and secular figures

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: there were two main textual versions/scripts of the hymn: the earliest Beneventan and the later Franco-roman

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: see above about the versions of the text

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: there are difference in the content of each script

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: by the church authorities of Rome (the most recent Franco-roman version)

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: probably an early christian hymnographic tradition spread around north Africa-south mediterranean lands

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: the hymn is chanted before the candle during the Easte Vigil

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: the hymn mentions resurrection and the manuscripts of the text illustrate Christ's resurrection

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– I don't know

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: God is illustrated as man in the manuscripts of the hymn

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: the features that apply to the Christian God of the Bible

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - No
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - No
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
 - Notes: saints and holy figures
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: the features that are related to the Christian God of the Bible

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: in liturgies and church rituals but see also other form of communication also

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: personal praying

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: there are illuminations of saints and holy figures in the manuscripts of the hymn

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: in general, probably through personal praying

1

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: features that are attributed to christian God

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– I don't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: spiritually

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
– Yes
Notes: at the illustrations of the hymn manuscripts

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– No

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: no

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: deliverance of sins

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - Yes
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - I don't know
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: belief in the Second Coming of Christ (Judgement Day)
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - I don't know
 - Notes: probably the faithful prudent and pure ones

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: chastity-virginity

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Notes: Virgin Mary-Mother of God

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: Virgin Mary-Mother of God

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only one gender

Notes: only to females -but this relates only to the Praise of the Bees part of the hymn

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: in allegorical sense

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
 - Notes: in an allegorical sense
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No

- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes
 - Notes: chastity-virginity

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: however, it is included in the Praise of the Bees part of the hymn as a virtue

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: however, it is included in the Praise of the Bees part of the hymn as a virtue

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: during the Easter liturgy

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: the attendees during the Easter liturgy

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Notes: a bishop/bishops

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: political and church authorities

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: no, the text was not destroyed

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– I don't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: it relates largely (but not exclusively) to males

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– I don't know

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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